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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****PREVALENCE OF DEPRESSION AMONG MEDICAL
STUDENTS**Sara Arshad¹, Ghulam Dastageer², Anum Jabbar³¹Rawalpindi Medical University, ²Bolan Medical College Quetta, ³Capital Hospital Islamabad**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Depression is a state of low mood and aversion to activity. It can affect a person's thoughts, behavior, motivation, feelings, and sense of well-being. A total of 120 medical and dental students were included in the study. A predefined questionnaire was distributed among the students. Day scholars and students living in hostels were included. The mean age of the students was 23.34±2.33 years. There were 60 [50%] male and 60 [50%] female students. A total of 90 [75%] students responded that they underwent depression during their career. High prevalence of depression is seen among medical students. So, there is a need to make policies and strategies for a healthier environment among medical students.

Keywords: *Depression, Medical Students.***Corresponding author:**Sara Arshad,
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INTRODUCTION:

Depression is a state of low mood and aversion to activity. It can affect a person's thoughts, behavior, motivation, feelings, and sense of well-being. It may feature sadness, difficulty in thinking and concentration and a significant increase or decrease in appetite and time spent sleeping. People experiencing depression may have feelings of dejection, hopelessness and, sometimes, suicidal thoughts. It can either be short term or long term [1, 2].

The core symptom of depression is said to be anhedonia, which refers to loss of interest or a loss of feeling of pleasure in certain activities that usually bring joy to people. Depressed mood is a symptom of some mood disorders such as major depressive disorder or dysthymia; it is a normal temporary reaction to life events, such as the loss of a loved one; and it is also a symptom of some physical diseases and a side effect of some drugs and medical treatments [3, 4].

Medical students are also exposed to multiple factors during their academic and clinical study that have been shown to contribute to high levels of depression, anxiety, and stress. University students face various stressors such as academic requirements, time pressure and social adjustments, and medical students in particular, may face additional challenges such as the large workload, the time commitment and the number of assessments, as well as the pressures of a clinical environment [5, 6].

A recent meta-analysis showed that depression affects approximately one third of medical students worldwide, and it is also likely that the overall prevalence of depressive symptoms among medical students is higher than that reported in the general population. Students with depressive symptoms also suffer from other psychological difficulties, such as anxiety, burnout, suicidal thoughts, and substance abuse [1, 4, 6]. The purpose of this study is to see the prevalence of depression among the medical students and explore the causes, and key issues.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A total of 120 medical and dental students were included in the study. A predefined questionnaire was distributed among the students. Day scholars and students living in hostels were included. Data was entered and analyzed in SPSS Ver. 25.0. All the categorical variables were presented as frequency and percentages and quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

The mean age of the students was 23.34 ± 2.33 years, mean age of male students was 24.34 ± 2.24 years and female students was 21.33 ± 1.33 years. There were 60 [50%] male and 60 [50%] female students. A total of 90 [75%] students responded that they underwent depression during their career.

Thirty students [25%] responded that they never had depression during their career. Out of 90 students, 75 were living in the hostels and 15 were day scholars. Main issues of depression as presented in the graph:

DISCUSSION:

Depression is major mental health cause of Global Burden of disease. Its consequences further lead to significant burden to public health, which include higher risk of dementia, premature mortality arising from physical disorders and maternal depression impacts on child growth and development. Depression and anxiety are amongst the most frequent mental disorders. Mental disorders have received increasing global attention because of their negative effects on working ability and the performance of people. As the core of the health system in all countries, medical workers are suffering from depression or anxiety resulting from their deteriorative treatment environment [i.e., workplace violence], overwork, burnout, huge academic pressure, declining job satisfaction, etc. [7, 8].

Similarly, as the successors of medical workers, medical students have reported experiencing a higher level of depression or anxiety compared to their peers. Medical students should be fully aware of the difficulties before entering into the job market. During the study portion of medical school, which is seemingly relaxed and enjoyable, medical students still experience huge pressure, such as the stress of the long length of schooling, academic pressure, the stress of clinical practice, etc. 27.2% of medical students, were subjected to depression or depressive symptoms

in 47 countries. Different prevalence results have been found in many other countries and regions. However, the determinants of depression and anxiety are similar, according to previous studies [9, 10].

CONCLUSION:

High prevalence of depression is seen among medical students. So there is a need to make policies and strategies for a healthier environment among medical students.

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